

VIRTUAL EVENT

5th International Conference on
**FUTURE OF
PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
AND PUBLIC HEALTH**

MARCH 20-22
2025

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

DAY 02

FRIDAY

MARCH 21, 2025

GMT - Greenwich Mean Time

08:20-08:30

Introduction

Sessions: Public Health | Preventive Medicine | Healthcare Innovations | Midwifery | Patient Safety | Digital Health | Primary Care | COVID 19 | Nursing | Internal Medicine | Family Medicine | Women's Health | Psychology and Psychiatric Disorders | Pharmaceuticals | AI in Healthcare

Distinguished Speaker Talks

08:30-08:50

Title: Living Habits and Public Health in Hong Kong: A Survey Study based on the Nine Body Constitutions

Hongyi Sun, *City University of Hong Kong, China*

08:50-09:10

Title: Indicators of Child Malnutrition among Different Social Groups in West Bengal, India: An Analysis Based on National Family Health Survey (NFHS-V)

Eva Ghosh, *Jadavpur University, India*

09:10-09:30

Title: An Optimized Deep Focused U-Net Model for Image Segmentation

Haroon Haider Khan, *COMSATS University, Pakistan*

09:30-09:50

Title: M-IoT Devices Optimisation through TinyML: Challenges, Advances, and Perspectives

Mohamed Maoui, *University of Oum El Bouaghi, Algeria*

09:50-10:10

Title: Ameliorative Effects of SesamumIndicum Aqueous Extract on Letrozole-Induced Polycystic Ovary Syndrome in Adult Female Rats and Formulation of Sesame Syrup

Zeynab Khosrowpour, *Shahid Beheshti University of Medical Sciences, Iran*

10:10-10:30

Title: Criteria for Enhancing Student Wellbeing in Stem Classrooms: ICT and Indigenous Knowledge in South African Higher Education

Nkopodi Nkopodi, *University of South Africa, South Africa*

10:30-10:50 Title: Prevalence and predictors of precancerous cervical lesions among women living with HIV in Libreville, Gabon

Mabika Obanda Alfred Keith Felix, *Universitaire de Libreville, Gabon*

REFRESHMENT BREAK 10:50-11:10

11:10-11:30 Title: Investigation the Role of Environmental Covariates in Geographical Distribution of Soil Biological Properties in A Semi-Arid Region

Ashraf Esmaeilizad, *Soil and Water Research Institute | Islamic Azad University, Iran*

11:30-11:50 Title: A Study on Body Composition Parameters and Biological Parameters of Farm Women working under Hot Climate

Surabhi Singh, *Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, India*

11:50-12:10 Title: Intelligent Medical Service Monitoring Health Care System for the Elderly

Sahar Ibrahim Ghanem, *Institute Pharos University in Alexandria, Egypt*

12:10-12:30 Title: Through the Lens of Experience: A Case Series on Pediatric Neuroblastic Tumors

M.Dougul Regis, *Institute of Child Health and Hospital For Children, Madras Medical College, India*

12:30-12:50 Title: Air Pollution-Related Mental Health Burden - Repercussions and Implications for Public Health

Ana Rodriguez, *Centre for the Study of Population, Economy and Society, Portugal*

12:50-13:10 Title: Universal Access to Sexual and Reproductive Care

Simona Astorino, *Italian Association of Legal Psychology, Italy*

LUNCH BREAK 13:10-13:40

13:40-14:00 Title: Pre-Operative EQ-5D-5L is A Strong Predictor of Meaningful Improvement in Quality of Life Following Primary Total Knee Arthroplasty

James Davies, *National Orthopaedic Hospital Cappagh, Ireland*

14:00-14:20 Title: Enhancing Individual Well-being and Community Engagement through Artistic Interventions in Urban Spaces

Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez, *Universidad Europea de Canarias, Spain*

FUTURE OF PMPH 2025

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SPEAKER TALKS

FUTURE OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE AND PUBLIC HEALTH

March 20-22, 2025

Enhancing Individual Well-Being and Community Engagement through Artistic Interventions in Urban Spaces

Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez (De Souza Sánchez, P. M.)

Universidad Europea de Canarias, Spain

Art-based initiatives play a crucial role in fostering social cohesion, strengthening local identity, and enhancing well-being. This study explores how artistic interventions in urban environments contribute to preventive public health strategies by promoting social interaction, cultural inclusion, and psychological resilience.

This research aims to analyze the impact of community-driven artistic initiatives on individual well-being and community engagement. It seeks to demonstrate how participatory urban planning, incorporating cultural expressions, strengthens the social fabric and promotes mental health.

A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative data from large-scale surveys (Redmond et al., 2019) with qualitative case studies of participatory art projects. Examples include The Roof, an ephemeral installation in Tenerife, and interactive public workshops at the La Orotava Science Fair (De Souza, 2024). These projects demonstrate how citizen participation in urban design fosters a sense of place and community belonging.

Findings indicate that art-based urban interventions can act as a form of social prescribing, improving psychological resilience and enhancing public engagement. Quantitative studies (Ma et al., 2023) support the notion that environmental design parameters significantly influence well-being. Participatory art projects empower communities, leading to contextually relevant urban improvements.

This table summarizes key benefits of artistic interventions:

FUTURE OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE AND PUBLIC HEALTH

March 20-22, 2025

Artistic Intervention	Community Impact
Public murals & installations	Strengthen local identity & social cohesion
Community workshops	Promote inclusivity & cultural exchange
Ephemeral architecture	Revitalize underutilized urban spaces

Figure 1 illustrates the influence of Art-based urban initiatives:

The integration of artistic practices into urban planning enhances preventive public health by promoting mental well-being, social inclusion, and civic participation. Future urban policies should embrace art as a tool for fostering resilient and engaged communities.

Starting point of this research: De Souza Sánchez, P.M. (2024). Sustainable Urban Innovation: Correlations between Art, Society, and Individuals in fostering Creative Neighborhoods. *Urban Identity Explored: Architecture and Arts in Cities*. Springer.

Biography

He is a PhD Architect with International Mention, holding a Master's degree in Analysis, Theory, and History of Architecture and a Graduate degree in Fine Arts. He is a Professor in Composition, Projects, and Urban Planning at the School of Architecture, Universidad Europea de Canarias.

His doctoral thesis, "The Fold in Architecture," is a historical, critical, conceptual, and experimental study on the application of origami patterns in architecture. With over 15 years of international teaching experience, he is a member of three Research Groups and has contributed to three R+D+I projects (one international and two national).

His primary research interests focus on:

1. Architecture and Design with Origami and Structural Folds
2. Educational Innovation in Architecture
3. Sustainable Urbanism and Cultural Development, particularly how art and culture serve as drivers for urban transformation.

Since 2000, he has worked professionally in architecture, art, and interior design, along with stage art direction and graphic design.

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